

6G-Path

D.7.1 Project website

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Glossary of terms and abbreviations used

Abbreviation / Term	Description
5G	The Fifth Generation of (Mobile and Wireless) Communications
6G	The Sixth Generation of Communications
API	Application Programming Interface
CSS3	Cascading Style Sheet level 3
D&C	Dissemination & Communication
DCM	Dissemination & Communication Manager
DoA	Description of Action
EEA	European Economic Area
EU	European Union
GA	Grant Agreement
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
GUI	Graphical User Interface
HTML	Hypertext Markup Language
HTML5	Hypertext Markup Language 5
ICT	Information and Communication Technology
IP	Internet Protocol
ISP	Internet Service Provider
KOM	Kick-off Meeting
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
KVI	Key Value Indicator
M	Month/s
SEPR	Search Engine Page Ranking
SNS	Smart Networks and Services
SNS JU	Smart Networks and Services Joint Undertaking
SoTA	State-of-the-Art
OJ	Official Journal
PPT	Power Point
URL	Uniform Resource Locator
W3C	World Wide Web Consortium
WP	Work Package
WWW, www	World Wide Web

Executive Summary

This document details the planning, execution and ongoing management of the 6G-PATH project website. It thoroughly covers the methodology employed for internal and external communication activities, including providing initial materials, templates and supplementary documents. The completed website is now accessible to the public at: <https://6gpath.eu>.

Additionally, the document outlines the administrative procedures for maintaining the website, ensuring continuous updates with dissemination materials such as newsletters, publications and results until the project's completion. It also explores the project's online presence, providing strategic insights into social media platforms for effective information dissemination and stakeholder engagement.

A significant portion is dedicated to examining the project's branding identity, encompassing logos, visuals, and key document templates. This section provides essential insights into the project's "positioning" and the consistency of messaging across materials.

The document concludes with a brief summary that encapsulates key findings and conclusions, thus offering a focused insight into the project's website and related communication activities.

1 Introduction

The deliverable *D7.1 (“Project website”)* is part of the 6G-PATH project’s *Work Package 7 (“Dissemination, Commercialisation and Standardisation”)* and focuses on the development of 6G-PATH’s visual identity, including a logo and style guidelines for both online and offline publications, such as the project website, presentations, technical reports and other promotional materials. This activity is aligned with the Grant Agreement’s objective 6, that is *“Disseminate and communicate results to a wide community of stakeholders while ensuring impact on standardization efforts”* [1].

The deliverable establishes 6G-PATH’s web presence and visibility as an important aspect of the project’s dissemination efforts. The website was launched in March 2024 (M3) and will be continuously updated throughout the project’s duration until its contractual completion, expected in December 2026. To support knowledge dissemination and impact creation, all public deliverables will be published on the website after final review by the European Commission reviewers and the website and its content will remain available for at least 2 years after the contractual “conclusion” of the project.

1.1 Mapping 6G-PATH outputs

This section aims to “map” 6G-PATH GA commitments, both within the formal Deliverable and Task description, against the project’s respective outputs and work performed.

Table 1: Adherence to 6G-PATH GA Deliverable & Tasks Descriptions

6G-PATH GA Component Title	6G-PATH GA Component Outline	Respective Document Chapter(s)	Justification
DELIVERABLE			
<i>D7.1 Project website</i>			
<i>Project website, available to the public, presence in the relevant social networks.</i>			
TASKS			
<i>T7.1 – Dissemination and communication plan and activities</i>	“[...] the objectives of this task are: (i) to establish and maintain a link with the general public and specialized communities through a public website, which will provide information on the consortium, project objectives, main outcomes, public deliverables and specific social networks; [...] Main outcomes: project website and social media channels setup (achieved in D7.1) [...]”	Chapter 2: Project website Chapter 3: Project social networks Chapter 4: Project branding identity	The document offers a comprehensive overview of the project’s visual branding elements, encompassing the logo, website, social media presence, assorted templates for deliverables, meeting reports, and minutes. It encompasses: A detailed description supplemented by screenshots of the 6G-PATH website. Insights into the utilisation of 6G-PATH’s social media accounts. An overview of the design and implementation methodology employed for the website. Details regarding the management and administration of the website. Presentation of the project’s logo alongside the templates utilized for diverse documents.

1.2 Deliverable overview and report structure

The document is structured into five chapters, as explained below.

Chapter 1 serves as an introduction, focusing on the objectives and accomplishments within Task T7.1 (*“Dissemination and communication plan and activities”*), led by eBOS.

Chapter 2 covers the project’s branding identity, thoroughly examining logos, visuals and key document templates that define the project’s image and message. This chapter is crucial for understanding the project’s positioning,

ensuring visual consistency across materials and conveying “key messaging”. It also provides insights into design choices aligned with the project’s goals.

Chapter 3 provides an overview of the project’s website, including details about the development methodology, content, and screenshots for each page. This chapter also includes guidance on website management, covering tasks such as content updates, page additions, or removals, as well as information regarding the website’s privacy and cookies policy.

Chapter 4 explores the project’s presence on social media, featuring screenshots of various accounts and offering a comprehensive view of the platforms used for disseminating information and engaging with stakeholders. Readers gain insights into the project’s social media strategy and can evaluate the effectiveness of online outreach efforts.

Lastly, Chapter 5 provides a concise summary and conclusion for the report.

2 6G-PATH branding identity

2.1 6G-PATH logo

During the 6G-PATH project’s logo development, the objective was to create a minimalist design that accurately reflects the project’s branding identity. In the early weeks of December 2024, the logo was presented to the consortium partners via email, who were then given the opportunity to indicate if they disagreed with its selection or if they wished to propose an alternative logo. Following this process and with no objections or alternative proposals from the project partners, the selected logo was confirmed as the “final choice”. The logo is depicted in Figure 1 below:

Figure 1: 6G-PATH logo

Apart from the project logo, all communication efforts and materials associated with the 6G-PATH project, including the website, social media content, YouTube videos, articles, presentations, flyers, press releases and publications, among others, will feature the EU emblem accompanied by the 6G SNS logo and a text acknowledging funding from the Smart Networks and Services Joint Undertaking (SNS JU) under the European Union’s Horizon Europe research and innovation programme:

Figure 2: EU emblem, 6G SNS logo and text of funding acknowledgement

A captivating array of visuals tailored for the 6G-PATH project’s website and various social media platforms has also been crafted. These resources, comprising compelling graphics, photographs and infographics, will be readily accessible to all project partners through the shared repository. These visuals are meticulously designed to offer maximum flexibility and can seamlessly integrate into diverse settings such as presentations, brochures, social media updates and more. Project partners are strongly encouraged to leverage these assets to disseminate information about the 6G-PATH project to a broader audience.

Some of these visuals are shown below:

Figure 3: 6G-PATH background visual

Figure 4: 6G-PATH use cases visual

In addition, graphics tailored for the project’s social media profiles have been created, ensuring that they adhere to the appropriate dimensions, as illustrated in the figures provided below:

Figure 5: 6G-PATH LinkedIn page cover

Figure 6: 6G-PATH X (former Twitter) account cover

Figure 7: 6G-PATH YouTube channel cover

2.2 Key document templates

The Dissemination and Communication Manager (DCM) has developed several templates to facilitate the project’s dissemination and communication efforts. These templates, after being approved by the project coordinator, have been uploaded to the cloud shared workspace under the “Templates” section within the “Administrative” folder.

The templates include:

1. A deliverable template;
2. a PowerPoint presentation template for the 6G-PATH project meetings, and;
3. a meeting agenda and minutes template.

2.2.1 Deliverable template

6G-Path

D.X.X Deliverable title

Document Summary Information

Project number:	101139172		
Project Title	6G-PATH: 6G Pilots and Trials Through Europe		
Acronym	6G-PATH		
Start Date	1 January 2024	Duration	36 months
Project URL	www.6gpath.eu		
Deliverable			
Work Package			
Contractual due date		Actual submission date	
Type		Dissemination Level	
Lead Beneficiary			
Responsible Author			
Contributors			
Peer reviewer(s)			

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D.X.X Deliverable Title

Revision history (including peer reviewing & quality control)

Version	Issue Date	Changes	Contributor(s)
v1.0		Initial Deliverable Structure	Deliverable Owner's Name
v1.1			

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Figure 8: 6G-PATH deliverable template 1/4

D.X.X Deliverable Title

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Table 2: Example caption for tables 6

Glossary of terms and abbreviations used

Abbreviation / Term	Description

D.X.X Deliverable Title

Executive Summary

Goal of the executive summary section is to provide a short summary for the deliverable and inform the reader on:

- The subject of the deliverable
- Summary of the work carried out
- The main conclusion(s)
- The purpose of the deliverable

Figure 9: 6G-PATH deliverable template 2/4

D.X.X Deliverable Title

1 Introduction

Goal of this section is to provide a brief outline of the objectives of the specific 6G-PATH Deliverable, how are those aligned and relevant with the overall project, and what was the approach followed in order to achieve them.

1.1 Mapping 6G-PATH Outputs

Purpose of this section is to map 6G-PATH Grant Agreement commitments, both within the formal Deliverable and Task description, against the project's respective outputs and work performed.

Table 1: Adherence to 6G-PATH GA Deliverable & Tasks Descriptions

6G-PATH GA Component Title	6G-PATH GA Component Outline	Respective Document Chapter(s)	Justification
DELIVERABLE			
<i>Dx.y Title</i>			
<i>Respective extract from formal Deliverable Description</i>			
TASKS			
<i>Task # & Title</i>	<i>Respective extract from formal Task/Subtask Description</i>	<i>Respective Chapters or Sections numbers within this document addressing GA described Task/Subtask</i>	<i>Briefly outline how addressed the respective document section(s) cover the described GA Task activities</i>

1.2 Deliverable Overview and Report Structure

In this section, a description of the Deliverable's Structure should be provided, outlining the respective Chapters and their content.

D.X.X Deliverable Title

2 Example Heading 1

2.1 Example Heading 2

2.1.1 Example Heading 3

- List example
- List example

Table 2: Example caption for tables

6G-Path

Figure 1: Example caption for figures

Figure 10: 6G-PATH deliverable template 3/4

Figure 11: G6-PATH deliverable template 4/4

2.2.2 PowerPoint presentation template

Figure 12: G6-PATH PowerPoint presentation template 1/6

Figure 13: G6-PATH PowerPoint presentation template 2/6

Milestones

5

Analysis & activities per task

6

Figure 14: 6G-PATH PowerPoint presentation template 3/6

Risks

7

Roles per partner

Column X	Column Z
Row 1	Row 1
Row 2	Row 2

Note: This is an example. Table colouring and type can be changed by each partner

8

Figure 15: 6G-PATH PowerPoint presentation template 4/6

Next 6 months plan

Note: This is an example. Smart art colouring and type can be changed by each partner

9

Next 6 months plan

Chart Title

Note: This is an example. Chart colouring and type can be changed by each partner

Figure 16: 6G-PATH PowerPoint presentation template 5/6

Figure 17: 6G-PATH PowerPoint presentation template 6/6

2.2.3 Meeting agenda and minutes template

Figure 18: 6G-PATH meeting agenda and minutes template

3 Project website

This section presents the project website, a central tool for the project’s online presence. The website’s design encompasses front-line technology like WebGL-powered dynamic 3D graphics and embedded content to improve the user experience, thereby rendering it visually appealing, user-friendly, and interactive. The website is a pivotal component of the project’s D&C strategy, and it provides “*information on the consortium, project objectives, main outcomes, public deliverables, and specific social networks*” [1].

The website is available at <https://6gpath.eu>. It has been designed to be accessible from any device and browser, serving the needs and preferences of all intended users.

3.1 Methodology for website design and implementation

The design and implementation of the project’s website was based on user interface design principles as well as on relevant requirements set in the project’s GA. The website’s user interface includes state-of-the-art (SoTA) design standards that warrant compatibility with various browsers and devices. The design and implementation of the 6G-PATH website interface incorporated the following GUI design principles [2]:

1. **Visual Appeal:** Aesthetics are enhanced by contrasting screen elements, organising them into clear groups, aligning them, and using colours and graphics effectively.
2. **Clarity:** Visual and conceptual clarity exists for elements, functions, metaphors and text.
3. **Compatibility:** User, task, and product needs are supported, adopting the user’s perspective.
4. **Comprehensibility:** The system is easily understandable, clarifying what, when, where, why and how to perform actions.
5. **Consistency:** Consistent appearance, usage and operation throughout the interface is maintained.
6. **Control:** Users are empowered with explicit control over interactions, quick actions and flexibility in customisation.
7. **Efficiency:** User effort is minimised with streamlined navigation, anticipating user needs.
8. **Simplicity:** A straightforward interface is presented with common functions prominent and unnecessary complexity hidden.
9. **Transparency:** Users focus on tasks without distraction from interface mechanics, keeping inner workings transparent.

The 6G-PATH website has been created by employing cutting-edge technologies like HTML5¹, CSS3² and JavaScript³ to guarantee a responsive layout, compatibility across various browsers and adaptability to multiple devices. This technological foundation enables seamless adjustment to diverse screen sizes and resolutions, ensuring effortless readability and navigation on any device, from smartphones and tablets to desktops and laptops. Moreover, utilising these technologies ensures compatibility with various browsers, expanding its accessibility to a broader audience. Built adhering to the latest web standards, the website guarantees both speed and security.

The 6G-PATH website has been designed to be the major hub for disseminating and communicating material about the project to relevant stakeholders. It is structured into several sections to provide comprehensive information. The website:

¹ HTML5 (Hypertext Markup Language 5) is a markup language used for structuring and presenting hypertext documents on the World Wide Web. It was the fifth and final major HTML version that is now a retired World Wide Web Consortium (W3C) recommendation. The current specification is known as the HTML Living Standard. For further relevant information see, *inter-alia*: <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/HTML5>

² CSS3 stands for Cascading Style Sheet level 3, which is the advanced version of CSS. It is used for structuring, styling and formatting web pages. Several new features have been added to CSS3 and it is supported by all modern web browsers. For further details see, *for example*: <https://www.css3.info/>

³ JavaScript is a programming language and core technology of the Web. Alongside HTML and CSS, almost 99% of websites use JavaScript on the client side for webpage behaviour.

- Provides an overview of the project’s background and motivation, its conceptual framework, methodology, objectives and details about the consortium involved;
- Presents real-world applications and experimentation scenarios;
- Covers various “avenues” for sharing project outcomes, including public deliverables, workshops, demos, publications, brochures, flyers, press releases, newsletters and video clips;
- Offers updates and announcements;
- Solicits participation or collaboration;
- Serves as a central resource for consortium members, and
- Allows visitors to find contact information for inquiries or communication purposes.

3.2 Website content

3.2.1 Website structure

The 6G-PATH website consists of various subpages/sections. The following figure illustrates the sitemap of the initial operational structure of the 6G-PATH website:

Figure 19: 6G-PATH website structure

3.2.2 Home page

The home page is the first page a user sees when visiting the 6G-PATH website. Its design includes all the website content, while the main screen features information about the project, including an overview of the project, the use cases and trials, the project objectives, the latest news, the consortium, the subscription to the project’s newsletter option, and a sitemap at the bottom of the page.

The homepage header contains the primary navigation menu and directs to the project’s social media platforms and newsletter subscription. This menu remains uniform throughout all pages, while the project logo serves as a link returning users to the homepage. This layout ensures effortless access to desired information and smooth navigation across the site. Designed with user-friendliness and intuitiveness in mind, visitors can easily locate desired content and explore the 6G-PATH project further.

Figures 20-24 below illustrate the 6G-PATH website home page:

Figure 20: 6G-PATH website home page 1/4

Figure 21: 6G-PATH website home page 2/4

News & Events

02 February 2024

6G-PATH kick-off meeting

[Read more](#)

02 February 2024

6G-PATH presented at the SNS Webinar "Introducing the Call 2 SNS projects"

[Read more](#)

02 February 2024

6G-PATH kick-off meeting

[Read more](#)

Figure 22: 6G-PATH website home page 3/4

Figure 23: 6G-PATH website home page 4/4

3.2.3 “About” page

The “About” page on the 6G-PATH website offers a concise introduction to the project. It can be accessed through a dropdown menu, which also includes links to other sub-pages such as “Background & Motivation”, “Concept & Methodology”, “Objectives” and “Consortium”. All content on the website is in line with the 6G-PATH Description of Action (DoA).

The “Background & Motivation” page provides an overview of the transition from 5G to 6G technology. It discusses the continuous demand for improved efficiency and performance in communication systems. The page outlines the goals of the 6G-PATH Project, which include fostering the development of new tools and products for 5G/6G networks from European companies. It explains the project’s focus on measuring key performance indicators (KPIs) and key value indicators (KVI) to ensure that advancements do “meet” industry needs. Additionally, the page refers to the project’s plan to collaborate with other projects aiming to share innovations and enhance communication technology further.

On the “Concept & Methodology” page, the project’s framework is presented, detailing its goals, methods and resources. It explains how the project will achieve its objectives and outlines the methodologies, procedures and techniques to be employed.

The “Objectives” page outlines the project’s seven main objectives.

The “Consortium” page presents details regarding the project coordinator and other members of the project consortium. Each of the partners is represented by their respective logo and their name. Moreover, when clicking on the partner’s logo, a new pop-up window opens up with the given partner’s short profile description along with the option of visiting the partner’s official website in a new browser tab. This page design facilitates visitors in obtaining comprehensive insights into the partners and their roles, and it provides effortless access to their respective websites for additional information.

Figure 24: 6G-PATH website “About” page

The path towards 6G is beginning now that 5G matured and is being deployed worldwide both publicly and privately. While 5G brought a step up in many fields, such as performance and efficiency, more is always expected in terms of efficiency by the overall community and in terms of performance by industry and technology providers who want to further increase their offerings and products. Continuous demands for higher throughput, lower latency and more energy efficient communications needs to be supported by relevant use cases that can claim and demonstrate the needs for these requests.

6G-PATH goal is to help foster the further development and integration of new and improved tools and products from EU companies with 5G/6G, while also measuring relevant key performance indicators (KPIs) and key value indicators (KVIs). To achieve this, 7 testbeds will be part of the project consortium, which will be used by 10 use cases spread across four key verticals: Health, Education, Smart Cities and Farming. Moreover, a relevant portion of the budget will be used for Financial Support for Third Parties (FSTP), where we envision the integration of 2 new Pilot Sites, extend the testbeds with 10 additional technologies, as well as 30 new use cases, through Open Calls, to further involve the community and obtain more metrics and outcomes.

6G-PATH plans to work closely with other ongoing/starting Stream-B and Stream-C projects in a feedback loop, where the innovations that partners are achieving in other projects can be deployed and further tested by our pool of use cases and Open Calls, while sharing our results and outcomes to further cement the innovation being made.

Figure 25: 6G-PATH website “Background & Motivation” page

Overall Concept

The 6G-PATH Project aims to foster the development of new technologies supporting 6G, both in close collaboration with other 6G Smart Networks and Services Industry Association (6G-IA) projects and through the process of Open Calls to engage European companies developing innovations for Beyond 5G (B5G) and 6G systems, as well as bringing new use cases and pilot sites to the ecosystem. Such technologies and pilots will be combined in relevant platforms to be used by a set of applications in use cases corresponding to the four verticals where 6G-PATH will be present: Health, Education, Smart Cities and Farming (in line with the Use Case Priority 2 of the Call). Such use cases and their corresponding applications will create demanding requirements from the platform, thus requiring a proper validation through KPIs and KVs. The work to be carried out in 6G-PATH involves the refinement of those indicators, which will adopt the work of the 3rd Generation Partnership Project (3GPP) Release 18 as starting basis, to closely align with the standards.

Overall, 6G-PATH will build an extensive B5G/6G infrastructure where a set of core architectures and domain-specific capabilities will be brought together and made available for integration of applications and use cases of relevance within the four addressed verticals, to conduct large-scale pilots and trials. The results of these pilots and trials will be collected and analysed in detail, to generate appropriate lessons and requirements for future 6G communications, as well as to identify, characterize and refine leading-edge business models towards the commercialisations and exploitation of 6G use cases and technologies.

Figure 26: 6G-PATH website “Concept & Methodology” page

Figure 27: 6G-PATH website “Objectives” page

About Consortium

The 6G-PATH consortium includes 26 partners from 13 countries, including 5 partners from industry, 8 academic and/or research organization partners, 1 NGO and 12 SMEs, which together bring to the project the full range of expertise to realize its ambitious objectives. All partners have broad experience in successful EU projects within comparable dimensions of 6G-PATH (e.g., size and ambition), and they have collaborated on topics related to mobile communications and 3GPP (4G, 5G and now 6G), cloud and multi-domain orchestration, verticals experimentation and open calls management and support.

This consortium leverages from past and ongoing collaboration activities, demonstrating the ability to comply with management guidelines, to understand communication and decision-taking processes and operational and technological requirements. All partners are aligned with the objectives and value of 6G-PATH, as well as the relevance of their own commitment towards the successful execution of the project. Each partner is aware of its role and its alignment with the project's objectives.

 orange Orange Romania ORO RO		
 AIRBUS <small>DEFENCE & SPACE</small> Airbus DS SLC ADS FR		
 KARLSTAD UNIVERSITY Karlstads Universitet KAU SE		

Figure 28: 6G-PATH website "Consortium" page

3.2.4 “Use Cases & Trials” page

The “Use Cases & Trials” page details the implementation of ten (10) use cases within the 6G-PATH project framework. These cases serve to test and validate both the 6G-PATH platform and its associated technologies, assessing their performance and advantages. These use cases span four (4) “key verticals”, that is: Farming, Education, Health and Smart cities. The project prioritises the inclusion of all sectors to encourage globalised business growth and advancements in applications aimed at integrating with 6G.

Furthermore, the project aims to “gather” a wider range of performance indicators, facilitating the formulation of comprehensive requirements for the transition to 6G.

Figure 29: 6G-PATH website “Use Case & Trials” page

3.2.5 “Dissemination & communication” page

The “Dissemination & Communication” page encompasses the various tools and channels utilised by the consortium for disseminating information about 6G-PATH and its outcomes. These include ongoing activities such as:

- Public deliverables
- Workshops & Demos
- Publications
- Brochures & Flyers
- Press releases
- Newsletters, where visitors can subscribe by providing their email and full name
- Video clips.

These pages will be continuously updated throughout the project with relevant dissemination materials as they are generated.

Figure 30: 6G-PATH website “Dissemination & Communication” page

3.2.6 “News & Events” page

The “News & Events” page offers real-time updates on all project-related news, meetings and events. This website section is regularly refreshed with new content, providing visitors an ongoing overview of the project’s activities and advancements. For instance, visitors can explore the inaugural post detailing the Kick-off Meeting (KOM) held in January 2024. Each post includes a detailed description of the event along with accompanying photographs, offering visitors a comprehensive view of project milestones. Clicking on a post opens a new window displaying the full text and images, ensuring easy access to additional information. The page’s layout facilitates seamless navigation, allowing visitors to stay informed and engaged with the project’s progression.

Figure 31: 6G-PATH website “News & Events” page

3.2.7 “Open Calls” page

The “Open Calls” page serves as a hub for providing comprehensive information about ongoing calls within the project. This page will be expanded to include all relevant sub-pages, including a dropdown menu for specific calls, such as the call for evaluators. Additionally, there will be an option available for applicants to access guidelines. This organisational structure aims to enhance clarity and streamline navigation for all users who visit the page. By categorising and presenting information hierarchically, users will find it easier to locate relevant details about specific calls and access guidelines as needed. Ultimately, the goal is to ensure that users can quickly access the information they need, facilitating their engagement with the project’s open calls.

Figure 32: 6G-PATH website “Open Calls” page

3.2.8 “Consortium hub” page

The “Consortium hub” page is designed to be a central repository for internal information within the project consortium. This section of the website will be restricted with password protection to ensure that only authorised consortium members can access its contents. Within the consortium hub, members will find a range of documentation and resources “tailored” to support their involvement in the project. This may include essential documents such as project guidelines, protocols and procedures, as well as guidance documents to assist members in fulfilling their roles effectively. Additionally, the hub may provide access to relevant templates, forms and tools necessary for project management and collaboration. By centralising these resources in a password-protected area, the consortium hub aims to facilitate efficient communication, collaboration and knowledge-sharing among consortium members throughout the duration of the project.

Figure 33: 6G-PATH website “Consortium hub” page

3.2.9 “Contact Us” page

The “Contact Us” page provides visitors with a simple and accessible method to connect with the project management team. It showcases a user-friendly contact form enabling visitors to input their details, including full name, phone number, email address and their message. Moreover, the page incorporates a GDPR compliance feature, mandating visitors to acknowledge they have reviewed and comprehended the website’s Privacy Policy before sending their message, ensuring the safeguarding of personal information.

Figure 34: 6G-PATH website “Contact Us” page

3.3 Privacy Policy and Cookies Policy

Upon loading the website for the first time, users will encounter an “Accept Cookies” option located at the centre of the Home Page, powered by the WordPress GDPR Cookie Compliance plugin⁴ (see Figure 35 below). The entire privacy policy, which adheres to the EU General Data Protection Regulation⁵ (GDPR), can be accessed at the bottom of the Home Page by clicking on the tabs labelled “Privacy Policy” and “Cookies Policy”.

The privacy policy (Annex I) of the 6G-PATH website forms an integral part of the website’s “Terms of Use”, focusing on handling personal data within the project’s website operations. This policy governs the personal data visitors provide to the project through the website and the personal data visible on the 6G-PATH website. It outlines the project’s commitment to processing personal data responsibly, securely and proportionately throughout its activities, in compliance with the EU General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) 679/2016⁶. Visitors can access the privacy policy alongside the Cookies Policy at the bottom of the page.

The Cookies Policy (Annex II) underwent a collaborative review and finalisation process with the project coordinator. Upon entering the 6G-PATH website and accepting the terms, visitors can access and review the cookies policy. This concise text provides an explanation of cookies, details the various types of cookies, outlines the website’s cookie retention policy, offers guidance on how to manage cookies, directs visitors on where to find additional information and specifies any updates – or revisions – to the cookies policy.

Figure 35: 6G-PATH website Cookies Consent pop-up window

⁴ For more relevant information also see, among others: <https://wordpress.org/plugins/gdpr-cookie-compliance/>

⁵ GDPR stands for “General Data Protection Regulation”. It is a European regulation that came into effect on 25th May 2018. It governs the way in which we can use, process, and store personal data (information about an identifiable, living person). GDPR is the *Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 April 2016 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data, and repealing Directive 95/46/EC (General Data Protection Regulation)*, Official Journal (OJ) L119, pp.1-88, 04.05.2016.

⁶ *Ibid.*

3.4 Online presence management and monitoring

3.4.1 Website administration

This chapter details the administrative interface of the 6G-PATH website. The site has been constructed using WordPress⁷ (version 6.4.3), a popular web-based software renowned for its focus on accessibility, performance, security, and user-friendliness in website design.

WordPress is fully compliant with GDPR regulations and boasts an extensive library of plugins that are regularly updated to align with emerging trends and user needs. The hosting for the WordPress platform is provided by Bluehost⁸, a leading web hosting solutions provider, ensuring that the 6G-PATH website runs on the latest WordPress version, thereby incorporating all the latest features.

The figure that follows illustrates the welcome/main page accessible upon administrator login to WordPress.

The navigation menu on the left-hand side of the website facilitates easy navigation across various categories within the 6G-PATH website.

Figure 36: 6G-PATH WordPress welcome page

⁷ WordPress is open source software. More details can be found at: <https://wordpress.org/about/>

⁸ For further details see: <https://www.bluehost.com/about>

Figure 37: 6G-PATH WordPress edit page

The administrator can view and modify an existing page’s title using the “Quick Edit” option. Additionally, they can create a new page by selecting “Add New” at the top of the page.

Furthermore, they can access and edit “Menu items” and “Menu Structure” by navigating to “Appearance” and “Menu” from the left-hand navigation bar.

Figure 38: 6G-PATH WordPress quick edit option

Figure 39: 6G-PATH WordPress menu changes option

3.4.2 Google Analytics – Website traffic

Google Analytics⁹, a complimentary web analytics service provided by Google, monitors website traffic and presents findings through Key Performance Indicators (KPIs).

The 6G-PATH website is enlisted with Google Analytics. This service furnishes an array of reports concerning website traffic, encompassing:

- Total sessions, users, and page views.
- Average duration of sessions and the proportion of new sessions.
- Demographic insights, such as sessions by country.

During reporting intervals, the analytics outcomes, accompanied by select screenshots, will be showcased.

As stipulated in the 6G-PATH project’s GA, certain KPIs pertinent to the website are delineated in Table 2.

Table 2: 6G-PATH website KPIs

Product	Indicators
Project web site, providing scientific papers, public project deliverables and software tools	Top 5 Search Engine Page Ranking (SEPR) >100 monthly visitor to the website

⁹ Google Analytics helps improve website performance by providing insights into user behavior, traffic sources and content engagement, enabling data-driven optimizations for better user experience and higher conversion rates. It can be accessed at: <http://www.google.com/analytics>

4 Project social networks

Social media platforms are pivotal for distributing and communicating project information to stakeholders, potential partners, organizations and journalists interested in tracking its development. They represent invaluable tools for engaging both a broad and targeted audience, thereby optimizing the project's impact and successful utilisation of its outcomes.

Notably, social media platforms like LinkedIn and X (formerly Twitter) are regarded as particularly effective channels for disseminating project activities and results to individuals interested in participation. LinkedIn stands out from other social media platforms due to its tailored focus on business and professional networking, where users primarily showcase their professional backgrounds and insights. On the other hand, X (former Twitter) offers a rapid and straightforward means of connecting with its audience, boasting over 421 million registered users and continuing to expand its user base.

In relation to 6G-PATH social media, according to the project's GA, they feature the following KPIs:

Table 3: 6G-PATH social media KPIs

Product	Indicators
Social networks posts, to take advantage of modern communication channels for wider dissemination	Number of 6G-PATH posts (≥ 10) Number of contacts (≥ 100) Number of likes (≥ 50 likes/share) Number of comments (≥ 2 com./share)

4.1 LinkedIn

In January 2024, eBOS, the project DCM, launched a showcase page on LinkedIn. This LinkedIn profile is regularly updated with the latest developments, ensuring each post is accompanied by relevant hashtags to enhance visibility. The LinkedIn showcase page is well-positioned to effectively promote the project and its progress.

Some of the selected hashtags for the 6G-PATH LinkedIn page are:

- #6gpath
- #6gpathproject
- #HorizonEU
- #eufunded
- #6GSNS
- #6GHorizon
- #6gnetwork
- #innovation
- #research
- #SNSJU
- #testbeds
- #6ginfrastructure

To amplify the visibility of the showcase page, project partners will collaborate on its promotion by leveraging their respective networks and followers.

Figure 40: 6G-PATH LinkedIn page – Administrator view

Figure 41: 6G-PATH LinkedIn page – Member view

4.2 X (former Twitter)

In January 2024, to broaden the 6G-PATH project's outreach, the project DCM launched a new Twitter account. The aim is to enhance the dissemination of project-related information and updates through this extensively utilised social media platform.

Some of the selected hashtags employed for 6G-PATH tweets are:

- #6gpath
- #6gpathproject
- #HorizonEU
- #eufunded
- #6GSNS
- #6GHorizon
- #6gnetwork
- #innovation
- #research
- #SNSJU
- #testbeds
- #6ginfrastructure

Figure 42: 6G-PATH X (former Twitter) page

4.3 YouTube

In January 2024, the project’s DCM established a dedicated YouTube channel for the 6G-PATH project to improve dissemination and communication with the public.

This channel will showcase compelling and informative videos created throughout the project’s duration, offering audiences an immersive experience and valuable insights into its goals and achievements.

Figure 43: 6G-PATH YouTube page

5 Conclusions

This document has provided an overview of the 6G-PATH project's website, serving as its primary online platform. Carefully crafted to be visually appealing and user-friendly, the website aligns seamlessly with the project's branding guidelines. The document includes a link to access the website along with details on its administration management. Additionally, it has provided insight into the design and development methodology employed in creating the website.

The document also outlines the various templates developed for the project, encompassing deliverables, PowerPoint presentations, agendas, and minutes' reports. These templates ensure consistency in structure, colour, layout, and content across all project materials. As part of Task T7.1 ("Dissemination and communication plan and activities") within WP7 ("Dissemination, Commercialisation and Standardization"), the website will undergo continuous updates with dissemination material until the project's conclusion in M36.

References

- [1] 6G-PATH (“6G Pilots and TriAls THrough Europe”) Project, Grant Agreement No.101139172, <https://6gpath.eu>
- [2] https://en.wikibooks.org/wiki/GUI_Design_Principles

Annex I: Privacy Policy

Introduction

This Privacy Notice will inform you as to how the 6G-PATH Consortium (hereinafter referred to as the “Consortium”, “we”, “us” and “our”) collects and processes information about you and in particular your personal data. We hereby assure you that this Privacy and Personal Data Protection Policy (“Policy”) fully respects and complies with EU Regulation 679/2016 (“Regulation”) and any other relevant legislation.

The processing of personal data, such as name, address or e-mail address of a data subject shall always be in line with the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) and in accordance with the country-specific data protection regulations applicable to the 6G-PATH Consortium. Through this data protection declaration, we would like to inform anyone concerned and the general public of the nature, scope and purpose of the personal data we collect, use and process. Furthermore, data subjects are informed, by means of this data protection declaration, of the rights to which they are entitled.

As the data controller, the 6G-PATH Consortium has implemented numerous technical and organizational measures to ensure comprehensive protection of personal data processed through this website.

Useful Definitions

- **Personal Data**
Personal Data is any information relating to an identified or identifiable natural person (“data subject”); an identifiable natural person is one who can be identified, directly or indirectly, indicatively by reference to an identifier such as a name, an identification number, location data, an online identifier or to one or more factors specific to the physical, physiological, genetic, mental, economic, cultural or social identity of that natural person.
- **Personal data breach**
Personal data breach is a breach of security leading to the accidental or unlawful destruction, loss, alteration, unauthorized disclosure of, or access to personal data transmitted, stored or otherwise processed.
- **Controller**
Controller is the natural or legal person, public authority, agency or other body which, alone or jointly with others, determines the purposes and means of the processing of personal data.
- **Processor**
Processor is a natural or legal person, public authority, agency or other body which processes personal data on behalf of the controller.
- **Processing**
Processing is any operation or set of operations which is performed on personal data or on sets of personal data, such as collection, recording, organisation, structuring, storage, adaptation or alteration, retrieval, consultation, use, disclosure, dissemination or otherwise making available, alignment or combination, restriction, erasure or destruction.
- **Third party**
Third Party is a natural or legal person, public authority, agency or body other than the data subject, the controller, the processor and persons who, under the direct authority of the controller or processor, are authorized to process personal data.

- **Consent**

Consent of the data subject is any freely given, specific, informed and unambiguous indication of the data subject's wishes by which he or she, by a statement or by a clear affirmative action, signifies agreement to the processing of personal data relating to him or her.

The Controller

Regarding the personal data in cases where as a Project Consortium, we determine the purposes and means of the processing, the Data Controller is the 6G-PATH Consortium.

Principles we adhere to

At the 6G-PATH Consortium, we are committed to and adhering to the following principles of processing personal data in accordance with Article 5 of the Regulation. The personal data is:

- Processed lawfully, fairly and in a transparent manner in relation to the data subject (principle of “lawfulness, fairness and transparency”);
- Collected for specified, explicit and legitimate purposes and not further processed in a manner that is incompatible with those purposes (principle of “purpose limitation”);
- Adequate, relevant and limited to what is necessary in relation to the purposes for which they are processed (principle of “data minimisation”);
- Accurate and, where necessary, kept up to date; we take every reasonable step to ensure that personal data that is inaccurate, having regard to the purposes for which it is processed, erased or rectified without delay (principle of “accuracy”);
- Kept in a form which permits identification of data subjects for no longer than it is necessary or as required by relevant Laws (principle of “storage limitation”);
- Processed in a manner that ensures appropriate security of the personal data, including protection against unauthorised or unlawful processing and against accidental loss, destruction or damage, using appropriate technical and organisational measures (principle of “integrity and confidentiality”).

Finally, we are able to demonstrate compliance with the aforementioned principles (principle of “accountability”).

Collection of Personal Data

The 6G-PATH Consortium as the Data Controller collects Personal Data from you within the purposes of research and the project's scope. So, in the following cases:

- When you contact us directly or indirectly (e.g., through the project's webpage and/or e-mail, or through our partners, or through our Social Media pages, etc.), in order to be informed regarding the Project or ask for relevant information;
- If you fill in any of our documents or subscribe to our newsletter;
- The 6G-PATH Consortium may also publish videos or photographs of images in case of events or workshops, provided that the relevant data subject gives its consent to the publication of it. There is no transfer of this personal data to third parties outside the same 6G-PATH Consortium.

Minors' Personal Data

We do not collect or process minors' personal data without verifiable parental consent in cases when we are able to control it. For example, it is not possible to control information that is communicated to us online. In any event, if we find that we have collected any personal information from a minor without verifiable parental consent (in accordance with Article 8 of the Regulation), we will immediately delete the information from our records. If you believe we may have collected information from a minor, please contact us.

Categories of Data Subjects

The categories of data subjects include:

- Partners of the Consortium.
- Users visiting the project website.

- Social Media users.
- Open calls participants.
- General Public.

Kind of Personal Data we may collect about you

Data from the following categories of personal information about you may be collected and processed per case in order to serve the purpose of the data collection and in accordance with the relevant legal basis as described in this Policy:

- Contact details with you or a natural person you may indicate instead of you (name, surname, address, telephone or fax number, email);
- occupational information (occupation, position);
- incident investigation data, such as incident details, data of persons involved or related information;
- information required by the institutional framework, such as personal data of persons depended or related to our Consortium members;
- apps/websites/social media related data (cookies, full name or nickname, information you publicly disclose and comments on social media, or email attachments);
- your picture when attending our events, or your photo is uploaded on our social media or website and of course in both cases under your consent;

Purposes of Processing & the Legal Basis of Data Processing

The processing of personal data is based on one of the “legal bases” as referred to in Article 6 of the Regulation (or Article 9 in case of special categories of personal data).

The legal basis on which the collection and processing of personal data is based (in most of the cases) are, the consent, the compliance in performing our contractual obligations, the compliance with our legal and statutory obligations and the safeguarding our legitimate interests. For special categories of personal data, the explicit consent, the performance of obligations and the exercise of specific rights of the controller or data subject in the field of labour law and social security/social protection law and for the assessment of the working capacity of the employee, medical diagnosis, the provision of health or social care or treatment. The legal basis on which the processing of your personal data is based, is as follows for each processing purpose:

Consent: When you communicate with us in any way directly or indirectly as interested in our project, when you fill in our documents, when informing you about our findings in the context of our dissemination activities, when you make a complaint or statement or when assessing us, when participating in our events, when you visit our social media accounts, or when you give us your business card.

Commitment to perform our contractual obligations: When you have agreed to receive our newsletter.

Compliance with our legal obligations: To comply with our legal obligations to all sorts of authorities such as labour law, regulatory authorities, tax, accounting, auditing, judicial authorities and agencies or in connection with our contractual obligations or during payment of our liabilities.

Safeguarding our legitimate interests: To improve our services, or when investigating and managing any potential incident, or for the assessment of persons and situations.

The Consortium is informed about the processing purposes and the legal bases under specific documents internally.

Retention of Data Period

We store personal data for as long as it is required by the respective processing purpose and any other permitted linked purpose always within the projects scope on completion of the project the data shall be stored until completion of the project.

Cookies are stored depending on their nature as you may be informed in our cookies policy linked to the present policy (please see below).

Personal data you disclose to us as users are stored for until the completion of the project.

Data that may be needed for our legitimate interests as a Controller shall be kept until the reason for storing such data ceases.

Specifically, for the data we process based on your consent (as an example for marketing), these are kept from obtaining the consent until it is revoked or there is no longer need to store it.

Information that is no longer necessary is safely destroyed or anonymised. We limit access to your personal data to those partners who need to use it for the specific purpose.

How we ensure the security of Personal Data

We have received reasonable organizational and technical measures to protect the personal data we collect and in particular any specific categories of personal data. We follow international standards and practices to ensure the security of our networks. We ensure you that your personal data is processed securely and legally, by adhering to policies and developing and implementing procedures in accordance with the purposes and legal bases of processing. For example, the following security measures are used to protect personal data against unauthorised use or any other form of unauthorised processing:

- Access to personal data is restricted to a limited number of authorised partners as per project structure and under the Data Management Plan and Ethics requirements.
- Our repository system of Microsoft Teams, used for the processing of personal data, all technical measures are taken to prevent loss, unauthorised access or other illegal processing.

In addition, access to these ICT (Information and Communication Technology) systems is monitored on a permanent basis in order to detect and prevent illegal use at an early stage. Although the transfer of data through the Internet or a web site cannot be guaranteed to be protected from cyberattacks, we work to maintain physical, electronic and procedural security measures to protect your data.

Some of the security measures we take are not announced for obvious reasons.

To whom the Data may be disclosed

We take measures to ensure that the recipients of personal data are kept to a minimum. The personal data we collect are disclosed to third parties, provided that the legality of such disclosure is fully justified. Specific personal data from those we lawfully collect as a Controller, may be accessed (or disclosed) on a case-by-case basis by:

- Any relating supervisory authority within its role.
- Any public or judicial authority where required by law or judicial decision.
- The auditor of the company, for necessary data according requirement (financial, employment, contracts and other controls), under confidentiality.
- The advocate, for whatever data is required in legal cases, under confidentiality.
- The Insurance cooperating company and only for the relevant part of the information.
- Partners' banks (of the company, the staff or affiliates and suppliers), only for payment related data.
- The training or systems consultants, the trainer, for training or systems control issues and only for the necessary pieces of information and data.

Territorial Scope

The personal data we collect is processed within the European Economic Area (EEA).

Your rights as a Data Subject and how you can exercise them

You have the right to be informed, the right of access to your personal data, the rights of rectification and erasure (in cases it is permitted), the right to restriction of processing, the right to data portability, the right to object. If processing is based on your consent, you may withdraw it at any time.

The right to be informed is exercised through this privacy and personal data protection notification. In some cases, it is also mentioned in documents – forms we are using.

We inform you that we are not using software of decision making solely based on automated processing including profiling.

Right of access: You have the right to obtain from us confirmation as to whether or not your personal data is being processed as well as other relevant information and, where that is the case, access to your personal data.

Right of rectification: You have the right of rectification of your inaccurate personal data as well as to have incomplete personal data completed by providing a supplementary statement.

Note: Since it is not possible for us to be aware of any changes to your personal data if you do not inform us, please help us keep your information accurate by informing us of any changes to your personal information we do process.

Right to erasure (“right to be forgotten”); we have to answer such right when:

- Your personal data is no longer necessary in relation to the purposes for which we collected it;
- withdraw your consent on which the processing is based and where there is no other legal basis for the processing;
- your personal data has been unlawfully processed;
- personal data has to be erased for compliance with a legal obligation we are subject to;
- personal data has been collected in relation to the offer of information society services.

We reserve the right to refuse this right if the processing is necessary for compliance with any legal obligation, we are subject to, or for reasons of public interest, or for the foundation and exercise or support of our legal claims (according to Article 17 §3 of the GDPR).

Right to restriction of processing: you have the right to restriction of processing when:

- You contest the accuracy of your personal data for a period enabling us to verify the accuracy of the personal data;
- The processing is unlawful and you oppose the erasure of the personal data and request the restriction of their use instead;
- We no longer need your personal data for the purposes of the processing, but it is required by you for the establishment, exercise or defence of legal claims;
- You objected to processing pending the verification of whether our legitimate grounds override those of yours.

Right to data portability: You have the right to receive your data in a structured, commonly used and machine-readable format and under an explicit request such data to be transferred to both, you and another natural or legal person who will process it.

Right to object: You have the right to object to the processing of your data at any time when the reason for the processing relates to direct marketing.

In the event that you make such a request in a written or electronic form regarding any of the above rights, we will assess your request and respond within one month of its receipt, either for its satisfaction or to provide you with objective reasons preventing it from being satisfied, or, given the complexity of the request and the number of requests at the given time, request an extension of response for a further two months period (according to Article 12.3 of the Regulation).

The exercise of your rights is free of charge. Where requests from you are manifestly unfounded or excessive, in particular because of their repetitive character, we may refuse to answer or charge you an administrative fee.

If you are dissatisfied with the use of your data by us, or our response after exercising your rights, you have the right to lodge a complaint with a supervisory authority.

Personal Data Breach

In the event of a breach of the security and integrity of the personal data processed, we will take the following measures (in accordance with Article 33 and 34 of the Regulation in case we are the Controller) and we will:

- Assess it in order to implement the appropriate procedures needed to limit the breach.
- Examine the extent of the breach and the sensitivity of the data included.
- Evaluate the risk and its impact on your rights and freedoms.
- Endeavour to reduce as much as possible the damage that is or may be caused.
- Notify within a time limit of 72 hours of becoming aware of the breach, the National Personal Data Protection Authority, if required.
- Assess the impact on your privacy and take appropriate measures to prevent the repeating of the incident.

In the event we are the processor, we will inform the Controller as soon as possible.

Links to other Websites

Our website may contain links to other websites that are not operated or controlled by us. If you click on a third-party link, you will be directed to that third-party site. We recommend that you review the Privacy Policy for each site you visit. We have no control over and assume no responsibility for the content, privacy policies, or practices of any third-party sites or services.

Cookies

By following this [link](#), you will be informed on our cookies policy.

Contact details with the Data Protection Authority

Additional information and terminology for the Regulation can be found at:
<https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EL/TXT/?uri=celex%3A32016R0679>.

Contact us

If at any time you want to contact us or make a request regarding your rights or any other matter relating to the protection of personal data you may contact the project's [email](#).

Policy Update

This policy is effective from 15/03/2024 and will be reviewed when there is a significant change. This review will be available on our website.

Last update: 15/03/2024

Annex II: Cookies Policy

In order to make your visits to our project Site as pleasant as possible, the 6G-PATH Consortium uses cookies. These cookies automatically track and collect certain technical information that your browser sends to us. This information might include Internet Protocol (IP) addresses, the browser type, browser language, Internet Service Providers (ISP), referring/exit pages, URLs, operating systems, date/time stamps and other similar information. However, this information does not identify individual users and we use it exclusively to analyze trends, to administer the site, to track user movements around the site “as a whole” to improve the services provided.

What is a Cookie?

Cookies are simple text files downloaded to your computer or mobile device when you visit a website or page, so the website can recognize your device the next time you visit. They are essential for easy navigation, making your experience faster, easier and more personalized. The term “cookies” in this Policy is used to refer to all files that collect information in this way.

There are many functions cookies serve. For example, they can help us to remember your language preferences or login information or analyse how well the site is performing, or even allow us to recommend content we believe will be most relevant to you.

There are cookies set by us called first party cookies;

A third-party cookie is a cookie that is associated with a domain name different from that of the page where the cookie is encountered. Third-party cookies are placed by the external social media profiles used on 6G-PATH’s website.

Third-party cookies are different from First-party cookies, which are associated with the domain of the page being visited.

Types of Cookies

1. Strictly Necessary Cookies

These are the most important cookies because they are essential for the operation of the site. You need them to move around our website and access many basic features. If you opt to disable these cookies, you will not be able to access or use the project’s website at all.

2. Functionality Cookies

We use functionality cookies to allow us to remember your preferences. They record information about choices you’ve made on our website, such as language, etc.

3. Performance / Analytics Cookies

We utilize performance/analytics cookies to analyse how the Website is accessed, used or is performing in order to provide you with a better user experience and to maintain, operate and continually improve the Website. For example, these cookies allow us to better understand our website’s visitors so that we can improve how we present our content or collect general and not personalized information about Website visitors such as what browsers or devices they are using, determine the number of first-time users, etc.

Within these three categories, cookies are classified as either session or persistent cookies. “Session” cookies are temporary and once you close the browser window, they are deleted from your device.

“Persistent” cookies remain on your device for a longer period and are used by the website to recognize your device when you return.

Retention period of the Cookies we use

The session cookies are temporary and they are not retaining after closing the browser window.

The functionality cookies and the Performance/Analytics Cookies are stored by Google to “remember” the user’s interactions with the website (Google Analytics) for a period not exceeding 2 years, while the marketing cookies are stored until the completion of the project.

How to control Cookies

You have the right to choose whether or not to accept cookies through the pop-up on this site. However, please note that if you choose to refuse cookies you may not be able to use the full functionality of our website.

Most browsers allow you to change your cookie settings. These settings will typically be found in the “options” or “preferences” menu of your browser. In order to understand these settings, the following links may be helpful; otherwise, you should use the “Help” option in your browser for more details.

Cookie settings in Internet Explorer: <https://support.microsoft.com/en-us/products/windows?os=windows-10>

Cookie settings in Firefox: <https://support.mozilla.org/en-US/kb/cookies-information-websites-store-on-your-computer?redirectlocale=en-US&redirectslug=Cookies>

Cookie settings in Chrome: <https://support.google.com/chrome/answer/95647?hl=en>

Cookie settings in Safari web: <https://support.google.com/chrome/answer/95647?hl=en>

iOS: <https://support.apple.com/en-us/HT201265>

Change of this Policy

We may change this policy to reflect changes in legal framework and in our practices and services. We suggest you to visit from time to time this policy for updates.

Further Information

We suggest consulting the Help section of your browser or taking a look at the About Cookies website which offers guidance for all modern browsers www.allaboutcookies.org and/or <https://developers.google.com/analytics/devguides/collection/analyticsjs/cookie-usage>.